

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

AI-Enhanced Laser Manufacturing: A Social Life Cycle Perspective From the White Goods Industry

Ricardo Mejía-Marchena^{1,2} | José Osorio-Tejada¹ | Abdullah Sert³ | Volker Hessel^{1,4}

¹School of Engineering, University of Warwick, Coventry, UK | ²Instituto de Estudios Hidráulicos y Ambientales (IDEHA), Departamento de Ingeniería Civil y Ambiental, Universidad del Norte, Barranquilla, Colombia | ³Arçelik A.Ş., Central R&D, Istanbul, Türkiye | ⁴School of Chemical Engineering, Adelaide University, Adelaide, Australia

Correspondence: Volker Hessel (volker.hessel@adelaide.edu.au)

Received: 9 December 2025 | **Revised:** 11 May 2026 | **Accepted:** 20 May 2026

Keywords: dishwasher machine | injection mould | laser texturing | plasma coating | social performance

ABSTRACT

Sustainable manufacturing transitions require companies to demonstrate not only environmental and economic benefits, but also measurable advances in corporate social responsibility (CSR). Therefore, we propose using a guideline-based Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) aligned with UNEP (2020) and ISO 14075 (2024) to evaluate the social performance of this transition in the case of introducing AI-assisted ultrashort-pulsed laser mould texturing in dishwasher manufacturing. The assessment covers 238 companies across the value chain and five stakeholder groups. Twenty subcategories were examined using conditional sensitivity analysis to capture context-specific changes, complemented by stakeholder weighting and pedigree matrix. Results suggest moderate improvements in social performance, primarily driven by enhanced occupational health and safety and improved consumer well-being. The aggregated score increases progressively across all scenarios, indicating a consistent positive trend in CSR-related performance under the assessment's assumptions. The findings suggest that S-LCA can support CSR evaluation in an advanced manufacturing context, contributing to managerial decision-making regarding the adoption of sustainable technologies.

1 | Introduction

Plasma coating is a conventional method for modifying polymer surfaces, commonly used to improve hydrophilicity. In dishwashers, plasma coating treatments have been applied to enhance the wetting behaviour of plastic parts such as cutlery baskets. As illustrated in Figure 1a, once the basket is produced by injection moulding, it undergoes sequential plasma coating steps involving the admission of process gases, plasma ignition and surface exposure within a controlled chamber. However, their benefits are temporary due to hydrophobic recovery, limited durability and demanding processing requirements (Okubo 2023). These constraints have motivated the exploration of alternative technologies. Laser surface texturing has emerged as a viable alternative,

imparting functional properties without the need for chemical coatings and feasibility for mass production (Gruner et al. 2024). In this approach, ultra-short pulse lasers (USPL) are used to texture injection moulds and the resulting micro- and nano-scale features are transferred to the plastic parts during replication. This process enables the production of durable hydrophobic surfaces with improved long-term performance (Alsaigh 2024). It has been successfully demonstrated as a reliable method for producing functionalised polymer parts with high precision and repeatability (García-Camprubí et al. 2021; Hernández et al. 2013; Lutey et al. 2021; Masato et al. 2019; Wu et al. 2011). Replicated surfaces show significantly enhanced water repellency, confirming laser processing as a scalable and environmentally friendly approach to plastic functionalisation (Bekesi et al. 2010).

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* published by ERP Environment and John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

FIGURE 1 | Comparison of conventional plasma coating and AI-enhanced laser texturing for dishwasher moulds: (a) Plasma coating process applied after injection moulding; (b) OPerATiC system; (c) Treated cutlery basket; (d) Resulting hydrophobic surface illustration.

Building on these advances, the OPerATiC project, a Horizon Europe initiative, has been established to accelerate the industrial adoption of USPL, featuring AI-assisted monitoring and real-time adaptive control, as alternatives to conventional surface treatments. As shown in Figure 1b, the new system consists of a physical layer, including laser amplification, beam delivery, metrology and dynamic beam shaping and a digital layer that synchronises motion modules, master controllers and planning software to optimise processing conditions continuously (Blanco-Filgueira et al. 2025; OPerATiC Consortium 2022; Pandolfi et al. 2025). Moulds formed by this system replicate precise micro- and nano-scale features onto the polymer part during injection (Figure 1c). This process eliminates the need for post-processing such as plasma coating. The resulting cutlery basket features a durable, hydrophobic surface (Figure 1d) that promotes faster drying and reduces household energy consumption. Together with existing techno-economic evaluations, these developments strengthen the case for lasers as a sustainable solution. Yet, achieving a complete sustainability perspective also requires understanding the social dimension, which remains less explored (Swathi et al. 2024).

In this context, Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) provides a framework to evaluate the social and socio-economic implications of these technological advances. It complements environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) by assessing impacts throughout product life cycles, from raw material extraction to end-of-life (Tragnone et al. 2023; Traverso et al. 2024; Wang et al. 2022). Unlike conventional LCA, which primarily focuses on environmental outcomes, S-LCA considers both human and social dimensions, assessing stakeholders such as Workers, Local Communities, Consumers, Value Chain Actors, Society and Children, while accounting for both positive and negative impacts (Muller et al. 2021). Since the release of the UNEP/SETAC Guidelines in 2009, later revised in 2020 and the more recent ISO 14075:2024 standard, the methodology has developed into a recognised framework for assessing social sustainability in complex supply chains (BSI and ISO 2024; UNEP 2020; UNEP and SETAC 2009).

To the best of the authors' knowledge, applications of S-LCA in large-scale white goods manufacturing are lacking, despite the sector's extensive supply chains and social implications. More

importantly, there is an evident lack of social assessment of new technologies and advanced manufacturing strategies, such as laser texturing, AI-enabled monitoring and plasma alternatives, making their evaluation particularly novel and relevant. By addressing these gaps, this study applies S-LCA to the dishwasher sector, covering up to 238 companies in the life-cycle system, to capture how the introduction of advanced technologies reshapes social outcomes for Workers, Suppliers, Consumers, Local Communities and Society. Although only one case of S-LCA related to laser technology is reported outside the sector, in agriculture for weed control (Michaliszyn-Gabryś et al. 2024), it does not adhere to UNEP Guidelines or ISO 14075, emphasising the lack of strong social assessment frameworks for such technologies. A similar situation is observed in additive manufacturing, where initial attempts to create social assessment frameworks are only just starting and remain quite limited (Naghshineh et al. 2020, 2021). Most recent S-LCA studies remain concentrated in other sectors, while assessments of household appliances are still predominantly environmental LCA (Gabriel et al. 2023; Hichier et al. 2020; Spreafico and Russo 2020). Thus, the goal of this study is to demonstrate how guideline-based S-LCA can be used to evaluate the social implications of advanced manufacturing strategies. These strategies include replacing plasma coating with AI-driven USPL, providing insights into socially responsible innovation in everyday products.

Summing up, although S-LCA has advanced in recent years, its application is limited, particularly in the white goods sector and in evaluating advanced manufacturing technologies such as AI-driven USPL. This paper addresses this gap by applying a novel guideline-based S-LCA to dishwasher production. The study employs a structured hotspot assessment and conditional scoring (α -values) to identify key social impact areas, while the discussion analyses how these methods reveal the consequences of shifting from plasma coating to AI-driven USPL. Together, this approach illustrates how S-LCA can capture the social dimensions of the adoption of advanced technology in large-scale consumer goods.

2 | S-LCA Methods

The S-LCA employs a systematic approach grounded in the International Organisation for Standardisation ISO 14075:2024 (BSI and ISO 2024) and the Guidelines (UNEP 2020). This methodology comprises the Definition of Goals and Scope, the Life Cycle Inventory (S-LCI), the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (S-LCIA) and the Interpretation. Figure 2 presents an overview of the methodological workflow applied in this study, illustrating how these phases were operationalised to assess the dishwasher manufacturing system.

Within this framework, the assessment first defines the goal, system boundaries, functional unit and relevant stakeholder groups, as well as impact categories and social subcategories. A hotspot assessment was then performed to identify the most relevant subcategories for the case study, based on sectoral information, contextual databases and company documentation. Data collection combined multiple sources, including secondary information for supply-chain actors, questionnaires and direct inputs from the main company and expert elicitation for the

weighting procedure. The inventory data were subsequently evaluated using a pedigree matrix to account for differences in data quality. The impact assessment phase involved scoring indicators at the subcategory level using the benchmark reference scale and aggregating results into impact categories and an overall Social Performance Index (SPI) using expert-derived weights obtained through the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). Finally, a sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the robustness of the results under varying scoring and weighting assumptions. Within the OPERATIC project framework, this standardised structure has been extended by introducing conditional sensitivity parameters (α -values) to capture the varying intensity of social impacts associated with technological transitions. This addition enables a more nuanced interpretation of social performance while remaining consistent with ISO principles.

2.1 | Goal and Scope Definition

The primary goal of this case study is to assess the social impacts of transitioning from plasma coating to IR picosecond AI-driven USPL surface texturing of injection moulds in the dishwasher manufacturing process by conducting an S-LCA. Consequently, our research seeks to analyse the potential socio-economic shifts resulting from adopting these novel technologies rather than just evaluating the sector's social performance. This study intends to support sustainable product design by evaluating potential enhancements in the well-being of stakeholders involved in the production and use of these dishwashers.

In LCA, defining the functional unit (FU) enables meaningful comparisons of product systems by focusing on unit-level processes and their environmental effects (BSI and ISO 2020; ISO 2006). Nevertheless, this is not the case for S-LCA since social impacts are primarily shaped by companies rather than processes, so the guidelines do not require it (Borri et al. 2024; UNEP 2020). Similar industrial settings might lead to similar environmental outcomes, but the social implications can differ significantly depending on local characteristics that are not reflected in unit-level process information (Singh and Gupta 2018). Although the findings do not directly relate to an FU, the following has been established for communication purposes: a standard-capacity household dishwasher, produced in Turkey, used and disposed of in Europe over a typical 10-year lifespan. The function corresponds to an appliance that cleans, rinses and dries dishware, glassware, cutlery and cooking utensils using chemical, mechanical, thermal and electrical means.

Up to 96 different components were identified for the dishwasher's manufacture; these were grouped into 12 different groups: mechanical components, electronic components, plastic and polymer components, metal components, sealant and insulating materials, chemicals, wood materials, glass materials, construction materials, surface coating materials and moulds from the injection machine suppliers. The system function is presented in Figure 3. The analysis distinguishes between two configurations: the current practice of applying *plasma coating* to the cutlery baskets and an alternative scenario in which the injection moulds are laser-textured by *USPL*, removing the need for plasma coating altogether. The S-LCA does not consider the extraction of raw materials because of the high complexity of the

FIGURE 2 | Overview of the S-LCA methodological workflow applied in this study.

supply chain and the project’s scope. Up to 237 different suppliers were counted in the assessment. For confidentiality reasons, the names of the companies and details of the dishwasher manufacturing process are not disclosed in this document. For the AI-driven USPL, the consortium comprises 16 organisations based in Europe (OPeraTIC Consortium 2022).

This research considered the stakeholders: Workers, Local Communities, Value Chain Actors, Consumers and Society. Children as a stakeholder, covering impacts subcategories such as *Education provided in the local community*, *Health issues for children as consumers* and *children concerns regarding marketing practices*, are excluded, as direct child involvement is not a pertinent social issue according to the project’s scope, based on the methodological sheets (UNEP 2021). However, education initiatives in the Local Community have already been evaluated regarding *access*

to immaterial resources and *child labour* was considered in the initial evaluation of the Workers’ group. Furthermore, it was determined that all methodological sheet subcategories linked to the mentioned stakeholders would be incorporated for the hotspot analysis. Although no new subcategories were suggested, minor adjustments were made to refine their scope and align it with the context. For the *Consumer* group, the guidelines overlook certain aspects, such as energy-efficiency interests that directly affect household operating costs. The subcategory *Health and Safety of Consumers* was redefined to capture this dimension as *Consumer Health, Safety & Well-being*. This redefinition was introduced as a methodological adaptation for the present case study, to capture consumer-relevant use-phase effects that are not fully represented by direct health and safety risks alone. Thus, this broader scope encompasses factors that enhance consumer well-being, particularly those related to affordability, convenience and

FIGURE 4 | Life cycle stages.

2.2 | Social Life Cycle Inventory Analysis (S-LCI)

The S-LCI was structured into three tiers, as shown in Figure 4, reflecting different degrees of data availability and detail. Tier 0 actors, corresponding to raw material extraction and other upstream suppliers, were not included due to limited traceability and scarce public information. Tier 1 consists of 226 companies supplying components and materials for dishwasher manufacturing. Although all companies were fully identified, a completed evaluation based on specific data of all social impact subcategories was not possible. Because complete firm-level primary social data were not available for all upstream actors, several Tier 1 indicators serve as proxy measures of company-level social conditions. In this context, proxy indicators were not intended to reproduce each supplier's exact social performance, but rather to capture the structural social risk or opportunity context. This interpretation follows the S-LCA methodological framework, in which contextual or generic indicators are frequently used to approximate likely social conditions within country-sector environments when firm-level primary data are unavailable (UNEP 2020). Such an approach is particularly relevant for large supply-chain assessments, where obtaining comparable company-specific social information for all actors is rarely feasible. Tier 2 covers the OPerATIC consortium partners, who enabled closer engagement and validation through direct collaboration during the project. The complete S-LCI for Tiers 1 and 2 is presented in Supporting Information S3.1. Tier 3 refers to the dishwasher manufacturer itself, where primary information was gathered through direct communication and tailored questionnaires covered all selected subcategories. While responses remain confidential, the questionnaire is included in Supporting Information S3.2. Regarding S-LCI for Tiers 3, this is presented in Supporting Information S3.3 (Table S3.1).

The pedigree matrix shown in Table S3.2 was used to verify that the data meet the necessary quality standards. This is based on

the proposed guidelines matrix but adjusted to align with the specific characteristics of the case under assessment. The matrix refines the data by considering key factors such as source reliability, completeness, temporal relevance and scope alignment. This way, high-quality data is fully considered in the assessment (multiplication by 1). In contrast, unlike a direct exclusion approach, lower-quality data is proportionally down-weighted based on the average quality from the matrix (multiplication by a factor from 0 to 1). This procedure allows heterogeneous social data to be incorporated while accounting for differences in reliability and representativeness (Tier 1 vs. Tier 3). Consequently, contextual or proxy-based evidence contributes to the assessment without being treated as equivalent to verified site-specific information. Final Quality Weighting Factors are presented in Figures S3.1–S3.5.

2.3 | Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment (S-LCIA)

We conducted a multi-level inventory assessment to analyse the various industries in the value chains by tier. In the S-LCIA phase, inventory results were translated into social performance scores using a five-point reference scale ranging from –2 (worst scenario) to +2 (best scenario), with 0 representing the reference condition aligned with European averages or regulatory expectations (Luna Ostos et al. 2024; Sigcha et al. 2024). A set of generic and specific indicators was proposed for each social impact subcategory, following the reference scale. Generic indicators, applied to Tiers 1 and 2, were normalised using a non-linear transformation based on the baseline. These indicators were selected from the *methodological sheet* to reflect structural conditions associated with the corresponding social subcategories, thereby enabling the assessment to approximate relevant social performance dimensions even when direct company-level evidence is unavailable. In contrast, tier 3 site-specific indicators relied mainly on the questionnaire's qualitative responses and the company's direct feedback. This distinction between generic

FIGURE 5 | Heatmap of Social Subcategories per Company. AM, Acc. to material resources; CE, Contribution to econ. dev.; CH, Consumer health, safety & Well-being; CP, Consumer privacy; EL, End-of-life responsibility; EO, Equal Opp./Disc.; FC, Fair competition; FM, Feedback mechanism; FS, Fair salary; HS, Health and Safety; IP, Resp. of intellectual property rights; LE, Local employment; M, Main company (Plasma Coating); M¹, Main Company (USPL, $\alpha = 0.1$); M², Main Company (USPL, $\alpha = 0.5$); M³, Main Company (USPL, $\alpha = 1$); PC, Public commit. to sustainability; PS, Promoting social responsibility; SB, Social benefits; SL, Safe and healthy living cond.; SR, Supplier relationship; TD, Technology development; TR, Transparency; WD, Wealth distribution; WH, Working hours.

and specific indicators aligned with the study’s scope, allowing the method to balance breadth and depth, capturing site-specific practices. When data were missing, a conservative score of 0 was assigned. In this context, assigning the reference value to missing data reflects the absence of evidence indicating a deviation from the expected regulatory or social baseline, rather than an assumption of positive or negative performance, avoiding bias against actors with limited reporting while ensuring consistency across the dataset. This assumption is supported by the Value Chain Due Diligence processes implemented by the main company, which establish baseline compliance expectations across suppliers and monitor adherence to these standards throughout the supply chain. This neutral value avoided unjustified penalties while recognising information gaps. In this case, missing data accounted for 11.22% of the overall inventory. They occurred exclusively among Tier 1 suppliers, where the score is the same for the plasma-coating and USPL AI-driven scenarios. No missing data were observed for Tier 2 project partners or for the Tier 3 main company, where direct engagement and primary data collection ensured full coverage of the selected indicators. This proportion is acceptable considering the scope of the study, which covered up to 238 companies across over 20 social subcategories. Around 75% of that missing information corresponded to indicators collected from secondary sources such as company websites, sustainability reports and codes of conduct, where disclosure practices vary widely. The remaining missing data resulted from cases in which national- or sector-level information was unavailable and no suitable substitute was available. The scores derived

from generic indicators were revised whenever specific evidence contradicted the baseline risk assessment. Qualitative criteria guided these refinements because the available information was heterogeneous across companies. These adjustments are presented in Supporting Information S2.1. The resulting values from the generic and specific indicators were weighted by data quality, following the pedigree matrix described in the S-LCI section. Subcategory outcomes are summarised in Figure 5. Complete datasets of adjusted scores were already provided in Supporting Information S3.1 (third element in each tuple).

A two-part sensitivity analysis was conducted to test the robustness of the social performance results. The analysis combined conditional scoring adjustments with alternative weighting scenarios for life cycle stages to evaluate how different assumptions influence overall outcomes. The first part introduced conditional adjustment to capture context-specific variations in social impacts. These conditionals were defined within the indicators and positive or negative adjustments were added. For example, if new technologies imply a direct reduction in working hours (as per the contract), a positive correction ($+a$) was applied; in the opposite case, a negative correction ($-a$) was applied. Parameter a was used to represent the intensity of these effects and three levels were tested (± 0.1 , ± 0.5 and ± 1.0), representing minor, moderate and a full one-level shift within the benchmark scale, thereby enabling a structured exploration of system responsiveness. Plasma coating was treated as the baseline scenario, while the AI-driven USPL was evaluated under the three a -values. The

complete list of conditionals applied to each subcategory was already presented in Table S3.1.

A uniform a -value was applied across all subcategories within each scenario to ensure comparability and methodological consistency across indicators within each scenario. In this framework, the parameter a controls the magnitude of the conditional adjustment within the benchmark scale rather than the relative importance of individual social impacts, which are addressed separately through the weighting scheme applied during aggregation. While social effects may differ across subcategories in practice, calibrating differentiated adjustment magnitudes would require empirical evidence and a structured stakeholder elicitation to estimate the effect size of these adjustments associated with each social dimension. As the technology assessed has not yet been implemented, such calibration is not currently feasible. The use of a uniform parameter, therefore, enables a controlled sensitivity sweep to evaluate how social scores respond to incremental and decremental variations in assumed impact intensity, while maintaining methodological transparency and clearly defined boundary assumptions. Results are shown in Figure 6, which compares the plasma coating and AI-driven USPL across the three a -values. The second part of the sensitivity analysis examined the influence of altering the relative importance of life cycle stages. For this case, we considered the Suppliers and the Main Company (Assembly and End of Life). The baseline weighting assigned equal importance (0.5 each), while several alternative distributions were tested to explore different emphasis scenarios.

To integrate the social impact scores into a composite SPI, we applied a weighting based on expert judgement across the five stakeholder groups, ensuring alignment with established S-LCA practice. Experts were selected based on their domain knowledge; the expert pool is reported in Table S4.1 (33 participants in total). Participants performed pairwise comparisons of the impact categories following the AHP (Saaty 1987) to determine the relative importance of each social dimension to be systematically evaluated. Responses were checked for internal consistency and when the consistency ratio exceeded the 0.2 threshold, corrections were made using Harker's method as implemented in the *ahpsurvey* R package (Cho 2019; Dolan 2008). Aggregation of expert judgements followed the geometric mean (Zira et al. 2020). The derived weights were then applied through a hierarchical aggregation procedure. First, subcategory scores were combined into category scores according to their local weights:

$$C_j = \sum_{i \in j} w_{ij} S_i$$

where S_i represents the subcategory score, w_{ij} is the local weight of the subcategory i within category j . The resulting category scores were then aggregated into the overall SPI:

$$SPI = \sum_j W_j C_j$$

where W_j denotes the weight assigned to the category j . All weights are normalised such that:

$$\sum_j W_j = 1 \text{ and } \sum_{i \in j} w_{ij} = 1.$$

The derived weights were then used to aggregate subcategory scores across the five stakeholder groups into the five impact categories according to Figure S1.1 and subsequently into a single SPI per scenario. Figure 7 presents the SPI under the default weighted scheme, comparing plasma coating and AI-driven USPL.

To further examine the robustness of these results, Figure 8a shows the variation in SPI outcomes under alternative weighting schemes for the two main actor groups, Suppliers and the Main Company, starting from a baseline distribution of 0.5 each. Figure 8b illustrates the relative improvement achieved by AI-driven USPL compared to plasma coating. Together, these results indicate that while subcategory scores shifted under different assumptions, the aggregated trends remained consistent, confirming the stability of the approach. All final weights and the aggregation structure are provided in Section S4.2 (from Tables S4.2–S4.10), with the derived priority indexes presented in Section S4.3 (Table S4.11).

2.4 | Interpretation

Tier 1 and 2 data were mainly compiled from secondary sources, while Tier 3 relied on direct company engagement and questionnaires. Completeness was therefore achieved within the defined boundaries, though uneven disclosure among suppliers introduced differences in data depth. Consistency was maintained by aligning all indicators with *methodological guidelines*, avoiding double-counting and ensuring traceability. Missing information was conservatively scored as zero, a choice intended to avoid speculative assumptions while explicitly acknowledging the resulting uncertainty. Some subcategories showed lower data quality, particularly *Feedback Mechanisms*, *Local Employment*, *Equal Opportunities*, *Wealth Distribution* and *Consumer Privacy*. In contrast, others suffered from a lack of disclosure by the suppliers (e.g., *Supplier Relationship*, *Social Responsibility commitments*). Part of the upstream assessment relied on contextual, or proxy indicators derived from sectoral and disclosure-based evidence rather than fully verified company-specific social performance data. In this regard, a limitation of the assessment is the uneven alignment between the selected proxy indicators and the intended social subcategories, particularly for Tier 1 and Tier 2 suppliers, partially capturing the underlying social constructs due to data constraints. To address this, the pedigree matrix was applied to explicitly account for data quality dimensions, enabling differentiated weighting of indicators. While the pedigree matrix and sensitivity analysis support the robustness of the results, heterogeneity in indicator alignment may still influence the resolution of specific subcategory outcomes. Accordingly, the results for these actors should be interpreted as evidence-informed approximations of structural social conditions rather than audited representations of individual supplier practices. Conditional scoring and weighting scenarios confirmed the stability of the SPI: variations in assumptions shifted some subcategory scores but did not change overall trends, which favoured the AI-driven USPL over plasma coating. The assignment of neutral values to missing data contributed to a conservative interpretation of results, as most information gaps were associated with secondary sources or unavailable disclosures rather than contradictory evidence. Future work could further reduce these uncertainties through deeper stakeholder engagement, improved supplier transparency and independent validation of social performance indicators.

FIGURE 6 | Social performance by subcategory.

FIGURE 7 | Impact category-level aggregation and SPI.

FIGURE 8 | Sensitivity analysis of SPI across life cycle stages and α -value configurations: (a) Global SPI results under various supply chain weighting schemes; (b) Incremental improvement of USPL over plasma coating across sensitivity levels.

3 | Results and Discussion

The results suggest that the framework can capture the social consequences of adopting advanced manufacturing technologies in the white goods sector. The adoption of AI-driven USPL appears to generate differentiated impacts across stakeholders,

as discussed below with a focus on Workers and Consumers (Figure 6).

The Workers stakeholder group shows distinct effects from the technology shift. The company complies with wage regulations and collective agreements; however, no wage adjustments are

expected as part of the technological transition. *Working hours* are expected to remain unchanged, consistent with legal standards and overtime compensation policies. The technology did not lead to shorter schedules or added flexibility, reflecting the limitation noted by Dachs (2018): productivity gains do not automatically improve working time arrangements. *Equal opportunities and non-discrimination* remained unchanged, supported by proactive policies and recognition, but the technology does not address potential structural barriers. While Singh and Gupta (2018) highlight the risks associated with inequalities stemming from new manufacturing technologies, this study did not detect potential positive or negative impacts based on stakeholders' feedback. *Health and Safety* scored proactively with a positive *a*-modifier, as manual strain and associated hazards are anticipated to be reduced without introducing new risks, aligning with Pandolfi et al. (2025). Finally, *social benefits and social security* maintained a moderate positive score because company provisions exceeded national requirements, although no additional benefits are expected to arise from the shift.

For the Local Communities stakeholder group, *access to material resources* is proactively scored at the system level, with ISO certifications and company initiatives on water and energy use supporting this performance. A positive *a*-modifier was applied, reflecting the inherent efficiency gains from eliminating plasma coating and lowering environmental burdens, with no new strain (Okubo 2023). Literature notes that advanced technologies can increase the demand for critical resources, such as rare earth metals (Michaliszyn-Gabrys et al. 2024); however, in this case, the impacts are expected to be marginal given the scale of the equipment and the replicability of the final baskets. *Safe and healthy living conditions* met the minimum requirements at the company level, supported by regular audits and a zero-tolerance policy. However, the system-level score remains under the reference point because it is derived from national-level secondary data (e.g., the Global Social Progress Index) rather than site-specific evidence, which limits representativeness. No displacement or outsourcing is likely in the short term, according to the company. Although automation is often linked to job displacement (Dachs, 2018; Singh and Gupta 2018), no adverse effects are expected within the scope of the study.

For the Suppliers stakeholder group, *fair competition* was assessed as proactive overall, supported by a Global Competition Law Compliance Policy and measures beyond legal requirements. No evidence was found that AI-driven USPL adoption may lead to predatory pricing, exclusive partnerships, or anti-competitive behaviour. The company also signalled its intention to promote higher quality standards across the supply chain. *Promoting social responsibility* was reported to be improved by eliminating repetitive plasma coatings and associated chemical use. The shift towards AI-driven USPL is expected to reduce environmental burdens in the plasma coating stage, reinforcing the company's Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) posture under regulatory and stakeholder pressure. This, in turn, may reduce environmental and occupational burdens across the supply chain. No changes are expected to *Supplier relationships* remaining on a proactive score, with Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) integrated procurement and oversight systems; no specific collaborative benefits for suppliers were identified due to the technology shift. Nonetheless, the requirement for

new technical qualifications and certifications might encourage adaptation and innovation capacity among suppliers. *Respect of intellectual property rights* is expected to remain unchanged, as governance is already embedded in ISO 27001 practices and no new mechanisms have been added to safeguard proprietary processes tied to AI-driven USPL adoption. No significant changes are expected in *Wealth distribution* since no evidence suggests the technology altered value sharing across the supply chain. Although literature highlights risks in this regard (Naghshineh et al. 2021), no direct indication of exclusion or inequitable value redistribution was observed.

Within the Consumers stakeholder group, the potential benefits of the technological transition were most apparent. For the *consumer health, safety and well-being* subcategory, the key benefit is the anticipated reduction in energy consumption during dishwasher operation, which lowers operating costs for Consumers and contributes to sustainability objectives by lowering resource demand. A second positive adjustment was applied to reflect the new extended hydrophobic performance of the baskets, which lasts through the full use phase rather than fading after a few cycles. This reduces the replacement burden, since baskets do not require repeated treatments or substitution if the hydrophobic feature is preferred, improving convenience and lowering hidden ownership costs for Consumers. *Transparency* remained unchanged between plasma and AI-driven USPL, as the transition is unlikely to alter reporting practices or contractual communication with Consumers. *Feedback mechanisms* will remain integrated into existing systems. While no dedicated new platform is expected to be introduced, a strong and structured mechanism is already in place, characterised by high responsiveness and integration. *Consumer privacy* is anticipated to be unaffected by the technological shift, as no new data flows or risks will be introduced; existing contractual and legal protections will continue to apply. The *end-of-life* stage is particularly relevant for Consumers, as plasma-treated baskets lose their hydrophobic properties more quickly than in the product's use phase, limiting their functional durability. In contrast, the AI-driven USPL alternative remains effective throughout the product's use phase. This extended lifespan reduces replacement needs and indirectly supports circularity goals, even though no recyclability data were available for the possible new materials in this assessment.

For Society, the impacts of the technological transition were modest. *Public commitment to sustainability* remained unchanged, with the company maintaining strong ESG targets, robust reporting practices and continued recognition. The transition to AI-driven USPL is not expected to introduce new public initiatives, but this is not ruled out in the future. Still, it avoids using chemicals in plasma coating, ensuring alignment with existing sustainability strategies without adverse repercussions. *Contributions to economic development* showed only a slight increase, with productivity improvements under AI-driven USPL detected but not significant enough to impact broader system-level indicators. The most noticeable change occurred in *technological development*, where the adoption of AI-driven USPL is linked to higher R&D investments and incremental innovation. These gains, however, remain limited in scale, highlighting a gradual rather than transformative effect at the societal dimension.

As shown in Figure 7, the trends remain broadly consistent with the detailed subcategory analysis when aggregating subcategories into broader impact categories. *Working Conditions* exhibited a modest upward shift for the AI-driven USPL scenario, with gradual increases across the different a -values. This improvement primarily stems from enhanced health and safety conditions, resulting from the elimination of plasma coating, which reduces manual handling and chemical exposure. The positive change in this category reflects a direct occupational benefit rather than a structural transformation, as no other subcategories within *Working Conditions* were affected by the technological transition.

The *Human Rights* category remained consistent across all scenarios because it is represented by a single subcategory, *Equal Opportunities/Discrimination*, which is unlikely to be affected by the new system. Since there are no expected risks, such as child or forced labour, human rights were not a key impact target, despite their significant weight in the analysis. This suggests that high-priority categories may exhibit no effect if not directly linked to the intervention.

The *Heritage and Communities* category showed a steady improvement under the AI-driven USPL scenario, slightly better than plasma coating. It includes *Access to Material Resources*, *Safe and Healthy Living Conditions* and *Local Employment*. Gains in Resource Access reflect increased efficiency and reduced environmental impact from removing the plasma stage, potentially lowering energy use without straining local resources. *Safe and Healthy Living Conditions* met national standards but lack site-specific data; future research should include community-level details.

Governance showed a slight positive change under the AI-driven USPL scenario, less than in other categories. The small increase suggests that adopting advanced technologies aligns with strong governance but doesn't fundamentally change performance. The improvement may indicate sustained compliance, transparency and adaptation, showing institutional maturity rather than structural change. This suggests the governance system remains robust amid technological shifts.

Socioeconomic Repercussions exhibited a more dynamic pattern, capturing indirect potential benefits distributed across Workers, Suppliers and Consumers. Improvements in this category stem from the aggregated effects of the expected enhanced Workers' *Health and Safety*, improved consumer well-being and estimated economic productivity gains. These findings suggest that technological transitions, such as AI-driven USPL, can yield system-wide social benefits, especially when coupled with improvements in efficiency and durability. However, as uniform a -values were applied across subcategories, the results should be interpreted cautiously, since the equal magnitudes of adjustments may overlook differences in the relevance of individual improvements within the broader social context. Nevertheless, the tested values correspond to minor, moderate and full one-level shifts within the benchmark scale, preserving comparability across subcategories while still allowing the aggregated assessment to reveal whether these incremental changes translate into broader improvements without introducing trade-offs across impact categories.

The overall SPI, presented in Figures 7 and 8, integrates weighted scores across all impact categories and highlights a steady improvement from the plasma coating baseline to the laser-based scenario. The SPI rises progressively from approximately 0.38 to 0.49 as the a -value increases, indicating a moderate but consistent social enhancement associated with adopting AI-driven USPL. This increase reflects the cumulative effect of incremental gains across categories such as *Working Conditions*, *Governance* and *Socioeconomic Repercussions*. Although the differences are modest, the clear upward trend across all sensitivity scenarios underscores the technology's potential to deliver social benefits without introducing trade-offs elsewhere.

The SPI is a composite metric that summarises complex, multidimensional social performance information into a single figure for strategic communication and decision-making. However, aggregation can mask differences between stakeholder groups and subcategories, so it should be read alongside category-level results to identify the true drivers of improvement. Sensitivity analysis shows consistent findings: the AI-driven USPL consistently outperformed plasma coating across all configurations, confirming robustness. The manufacturing stage contributes most to the SPI, reflecting technological improvements and benefits for workers and consumers. Even at lower a -values, the difference in SPI remained positive.

This study shows that integrating advanced manufacturing technologies, like AI-driven USPL, can bring meaningful social improvements within established production systems. Instead of radical social change, the shift from plasma coating to AI-driven USPL highlights how innovation can reinforce social stability while improving occupational safety, process reliability and product value. Social progress in mature sectors can come from incremental technological changes guided by responsible design. For manufacturers, adopting cleaner, precise technologies supports competitiveness and credibility.

4 | Conclusions

We examined the social implications of implementing AI-driven USPL surface texturing to replace plasma coating in the white goods sector, applying an S-LCA aligned with the UNEP 2020 Guidelines and ISO 14075:2024 framework. Most S-LCA studies rely on sector- or national-level indicators tied to Value Chain Actors. While useful, this approach can obscure firm-level changes from adopting new technologies. Structural bias was a concern in this case, as stronger indicators in developed economies could overshadow specific shifts introduced by the new process. By applying conditional scoring (a -values) to Tier 3 qualitative inputs, this study captured subtler potential changes in social performance, including those related to worker conditions, productivity and consumer well-being. The results suggest that integrating AI-driven USPL into large-scale appliance manufacturing may lead to meaningful social improvements. The most relevant expected changes were observed in *Working Conditions*, *Governance* and *Socioeconomic Repercussions*, indicating that advanced technologies can enhance occupational safety, process reliability and value creation without disrupting the existing supply chain. The findings also indicate that technological innovation in mature industrial sectors can strengthen

social responsibility by promoting cleaner production, reducing chemical use and improving resource efficiency. These advances reflect how focused process-level innovation can deliver measurable social benefits alongside environmental and economic gains. Applying an ISO-aligned S-LCA framework, this study shows that these social assessment methods effectively capture the societal impact of advanced manufacturing in high-volume production. Future research should expand to other manufacturing technologies and industries, involving more stakeholders, calibrate the conditional and long-term analysis to track social benefits as technologies develop.

Acknowledgements

The Authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the OPeraTIC consortium. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. OPeraTIC is a Horizon Europe project supported by the European Commission under grant agreement No. 101058409 and the UK Research and Innovation Reference Number 10055621.

Funding

This work was supported by the European Commission (101058409) and the UK Research and Innovation (10055621).

Disclosure

The authors have nothing to report.

Ethics Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

Consent

The authors have nothing to report.

Data Availability Statement

Data are provided in the [Supporting Information](#).

References

- Alsaigh, R. A. 2024. "Enhancement of Surface Properties Using Ultrashort-Pulsed-Laser Texturing: A Review." *Crystals* 14, no. 4: 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst14040353>.
- Bekesi, J., J. J. J. Kaakkunen, W. Michaeli, et al. 2010. "Fast Fabrication of Super-Hydrophobic Surfaces on Polypropylene by Replication of Short-Pulse Laser Structured Molds." *Applied Physics A: Materials Science and Processing* 99, no. 4: 691–695. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-010-5719-8>.
- Benoit-Norris, C., D. A. Cavan, and G. Norris. 2012. "Identifying Social Impacts in Product Supply Chains: Overview and Application of the Social Hotspot Database." *Sustainability* 4, no. 9: 1946–1965. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su4091946>.
- BHRR. 2024. *Company Index Page*. <https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/companies/>.
- Blanco-Filgueira, B., T. Delgado, A. Gregores Coto, et al. 2025. "Synthetic Data for AI-Powered Ultrafast Laser Based Micro-Structuring Method Description." In *Advances in Artificial Intelligence in Manufacturing II*, edited by K. Alexopoulos, S. Makris, and P. Stavropoulos, 48–59. Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-86489-6_6.

Borri, E., G. Zsembinski, and L. F. Cabeza. 2024. "Evaluation of the Social Impact of an Energy System for Residential Heating Applications Based on a Novel Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage." *Journal of Energy Storage* 86: 111210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.111210>.

BSI, & ISO. 2020. *BS EN ISO 14040:2006+A1:2020—Environmental Management – Life Cycle Assessment – Principles and Framework*. BSI Standards Limited.

BSI, & ISO. 2024. *BS ISO 14075:2024—Environmental Management—Principles and Framework for Social Life Cycle Assessment*. BSI Standards Limited.

Cho, F. 2019. ahpsurvey: Analytic Hierarchy Process for Survey Data. In CRAN: Contributed Packages. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/ahpsurvey/index.html>.

Dachs, B. 2018. "Impact of New Technologies on the Labour Market and the Social Economy." *European Parliamentary Research Service, Scientific Foresight Unit (STOA)*. <https://doi.org/10.2861/68448>.

Dolan, J. G. 2008. "Shared Decision-Making: Transferring Research Into Practice: The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)." *Patient Education and Counseling* 73, no. 3: 418–425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2008.07.032>.

Gabriel, C., N. B. Rodríguez, R. Gaha, A. Mio, and C. Favi. 2023. "Design Metrics to Normalize and Compare LCA Results in Household Appliance Sector: Outcomes From Literature Analysis." *Procedia CIRP* 116: 612–617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2023.02.103>.

García-Camprubí, M., C. Alfaro-Isac, B. Hernández-Gascón, J. R. Valdés, and S. Izquierdo. 2021. "Numerical Approach for the Assessment of Micro-Textured Walls Effects on Rubber Injection Moulding." *Polymers* 13, no. 11: 1739. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13111739>.

Gruner, A., J. Schille, and U. Loeschner. 2024. "Ultrashort Pulse Laser Surface Texturing for Injection Mold Functionalization." *Journal of Laser Micro/Nanoengineering* 19, no. 1: 20–26. <https://doi.org/10.2961/jlmn.2024.01.2003>.

Hernández, P., A. Murawko, J. Martínez, G. Peláez, and E. Ares. 2013. "Replication of Micro Laser Textures by Injection Molding." *Procedia Engineering* 63: 885–894. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2013.08.201>.

Hischier, R., F. Reale, V. Castellani, and S. Sala. 2020. "Environmental Impacts of Household Appliances in Europe and Scenarios for Their Impact Reduction." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 267: 121952. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121952>.

ISO. 2006. *14040:2006: Environmental Management -Life Cycle Assessment—Principles and Framework*.

Luna Ostos, L. M., L. Roche, V. Coroama, and M. Finkbeiner. 2024. "Social Life Cycle Assessment in the Chocolate Industry: A Colombian Case Study With Luker Chocolate." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 29, no. 5: 929–951. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-023-02261-y>.

Lutey, A. H. A., G. Lazzini, L. Gemini, et al. 2021. "Insight Into Replication Effectiveness of Laser-Textured Micro and Nanoscale Morphology by Injection Molding." *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 65: 445–454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.03.046>.

Masato, D., M. Sorgato, A. Batal, S. Dimov, and G. Lucchetta. 2019. "Thin-Wall Injection Molding of Polypropylene Using Molds With Different Laser-Induced Periodic Surface Structures." *Polymer Engineering and Science* 59, no. 9: 1889–1896. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.25189>.

Michaliszyn-Gabryś, B., J. Bronder, and J. Krupanek. 2024. "Social Life Cycle Assessment of Laser Weed Control System: A Case Study." *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 16, no. 6: 2590. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062590>.

Muller, S., A. Beylot, O. Sydd, K. Doyle, J. Bodin, and J. Villeneuve. 2021. "Applying Social Life Cycle Assessment in the Early Stages of a Project Development—An Example From the Mining Sector." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 26, no. 12: 2436–2456. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-021-01995-x>.

- Naghshineh, B., F. Lourenço, R. Godina, C. Jacinto, and H. Carvalho. 2020. "A Social Life Cycle Assessment Framework for Additive Manufacturing Products." *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)* 10, no. 13: 4459. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10134459>.
- Naghshineh, B., A. Ribeiro, C. Jacinto, and H. Carvalho. 2021. "Social Impacts of Additive Manufacturing: A Stakeholder-Driven Framework." *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 164: 120368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120368>.
- Okubo, M. 2023. "Nonthermal Plasma Surface Modification of Materials." In *Nonthermal Plasma Surface Modification of Materials*. Springer Nature. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-4506-1>.
- OPeraTIC Consortium. 2022. "Boosting the Adoption of Ultrashort Pulsed Laser Large Scale Structuring With an Agile, Dexterous and Efficient Manufacturing Platform." In *Horizon Europe Project No. 101058409*. European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.3030/101058409>.
- Pandolfi, A., S. Ferrarini, P. Bilancia, and M. Pellicciari. 2025. "Virtual Prototyping of a Novel Manipulator for Efficient Laser Processing of Complex Large Parts." *Machines* 13, no. 3: 176. <https://doi.org/10.3390/machines13030176>.
- Saaty, R. W. 1987. "The Analytic Hierarchy Process: What It Is and How It Is Used." *Mathematical Modelling* 9, no. 5: 161–176.
- Sigcha, E., D. Sucozhañay, L. Siguenza-Guzman, and P. Vanegas. 2024. "Evaluating the Social Performance of Ecuadorian Textile MSMEs Using Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment." *Cleaner Environmental Systems* 12: 100176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesys.2024.100176>.
- Singh, R. K., and U. Gupta. 2018. "Social Life Cycle Assessment in Indian Steel Sector: A Case Study." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 23, no. 4: 921–939. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-017-1427-3>.
- Spreafico, C., and D. Russo. 2020. "Assessing Domestic Environmental Impacts Through LCA Using Data From the Scientific Literature." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 266: 121883. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121883>.
- Swathi, B., S. V. Polyakov, S. R. Kandavalli, D. K. Singh, M. Y. B. Murthy, and A. Gopi. 2024. "Enhancing Hybrid Manufacturing With AI-Driven Real-Time Adaptive Process Control: Integrating Machine Learning Models and Robotic Systems." *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-024-14155-w>.
- Tragnone, B. M., M. Serreli, I. Arzoumanidis, C. A. Pelino, and L. Petti. 2023. "Using the Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment (PSILCA) Database for Product Comparison: Confetti Case Study." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 28, no. 8: 1031–1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-023-02173-x>.
- Traverso, M., R. Mankaa, M. Concetta Pedalá, and A. Covais. 2024. "Social Hotspot Analysis of the e-Waste Sector in Ghana and Nigeria." *Waste Management* 183: 271–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2024.05.023>.
- UNEP. 2020. Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations.
- UNEP. 2021. Methodological Sheets for Subcategories in Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) 2021.
- UNEP, & SETAC. 2009. *Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products*. United Nations Environment Programme.
- Wang, S., D. Su, and Y. Wu. 2022. "Environmental and Social Life Cycle Assessments of an Industrial LED Lighting Product." *Environmental Impact Assessment Review* 95: 106804. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2022.106804>.
- Wu, P. H., C. W. Cheng, C. P. Chang, T. M. Wu, and J. K. Wang. 2011. "Fabrication of Large-Area Hydrophobic Surfaces With Femtosecond-Laser-Structured Molds." *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering* 21, no. 11: 115032. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0960-1317/21/11/115032>.
- Zira, S., E. Rööös, E. Ivarsson, R. Hoffmann, and L. Rydhmer. 2020. "Social Life Cycle Assessment of Swedish Organic and Conventional Pork Production." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 25, no. 10: 1957–1975. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-020-01811-y>.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Figure S1:1.** List of Social Impact categories and Subcategories. **Table S1:1.** S-LCA Social impact subcategories, specific and generic indicators. **Table S2:1.** Social Hotspot Database Indicators per sector and country. **Table S2:2.** The Business and Human Resources Centre reports on companies. **Table S3:1.** Inventory for Tier 3. **Table S3:2.** Pedigree Matrix. **Figure S3:1.** Quality Weighting Factors (Averages). **Figure S3:2.** Quality Weighting Factors (Reliability of the source). **Figure S3:3.** Quality Weighting Factors (Completeness conformance). **Figure S3:4.** Quality Weighting Factors (Temporal conformance). **Figure S3:5.** Quality Weighting Factors (Scope Alignment). **Table S4:1.** Pool of experts for AHP. **Table S4:2.** Value Chain Actors: Socioeconomic Repercussions. **Table S4:3.** Value Chain Actors: Governance. **Table S4:4.** Society: Socioeconomic repercussion. **Table S4:5.** Local Communities: Heritage and Communities. **Table S4:6.** Workers: Human Rights & Working Conditions. **Table S4:7.** Consumers: Governance. **Table S4:8.** Society: Socioeconomic repercussion. **Table S4:9.** Subcategories related to Socioeconomic repercussion. **Table S4:10.** Social Impact categories. **Table S4:11.** displays the final priority indexes derived from the AHP process across two hierarchical levels. The first column, 'Priority Indexes¹', shows the normalised weights assigned to each impact category (Human Rights, Working Conditions, Heritage and Communities, Governance and Socioeconomic Repercussions), which are used to aggregate category scores into the overall Social Performance Index (SPI). These weights sum to 100% within each category. The second column, 'Priority Indexes²', indicates the local priority weights for each subcategory within its respective category. These subcategory weights are normalised within each category and are used to combine subcategory scores into category-level scores before calculating the SPI. Hence, subcategory weights emphasise the importance within their specific categories rather than across all categories. **Table S4:11.** Priority Indexes.